

Vanadium. Part II. Benzohydroxamic Acid Complexes

R. L. Dutta* and Subrata Lahiry

Benzohydroxamic acid (RH₂) reacts with quadri- and quinque-valent vanadium to form compounds (I) [VO(RH)₃] and (II) [VO(OH)(RH)₂] in rose and violet-black colour respectively. Both these compounds dissolve in boiling alcohols (methyl, ethyl and isopropyl) yielding red solutions from which silky brick-red crystals of composition, [VO(OX)(RH)₂] (III), have been characterised. Besides, violet-black complexes of the type M[VO(OH)(R)₂] where M = a bivalent cation such as Ba²⁺, [Cu(Big)₂]²⁺ or [Cu(Gau)₂]²⁺ have also been prepared. Compound (I) is paramagnetic, whereas others are diamagnetic. Structural dispositions of the functional group of the ligand have also been related from the IR spectra of the potassium salt of the ligand and the complexes.

Job's method of continued variation between traces of vanadate and benzohydroxamic acid at pH 3.5 in aqueous ethanol medium indicates a 1:3 complex. Further variation studies between the ester (III) and the reagent under the same condition indicate a 1:1 complex and confirm the earlier finding.

Following early literature reports on the formation of deeply coloured ferric complexes with hydroxamic acids, in general, and some salts with Cu, Ni, Co, Zr, Th, etc.¹, Musante², Das Gupta and Singh³, and Rây and Bhaduri⁴ reported the analytical uses of benzohydroxamic acid and of salicylhydroxamic acid. Benzohydroxamic acid was found to develop a highly coloured orange-red product with traces of vanadate in aqueous ethanol at a pH (ca.) 3-5. This was utilised by Das Gupta and Singh³ for a sensitive colorimetric method for determination of traces of vanadium. Wise and Brandt⁵ afterwards made this method more sensitive by extracting the vanadium complex with hexanol⁶. Rây and Bhaduri⁴ in a preliminary exploration of the usefulness of salicylhydroxamic acid as a colorimetric reagent for uranium, vanadium, and molybdenum postulated the blue-violet vanadium complex as H₂[VO(C₇H₅O₃N)₂]. They⁴ later described the complex as one of quinquevalent vanadium, though no details of its preparation or properties were, however, reported. Oxalohydroxamic acid was also utilised for the indirect colorimetric estimation of calcium and zirconium⁶. Recently, a systematic study of pyridine- and quinoline-hydroxamic acids as spectrophotometric reagents for manganese, iron,

*Present address: Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan, Burdwan.

1. Hodges, *Annalen*, 1876, **182**, 214; Jesrenand, *Ber.*, 1889, **22**, 1270; Jones and Hurd, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 2422; Lossen, *Annalen*, 1860, **150**, 314, 1872, **161**, 347; Pickard *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, **81**, 1563; Ponzio and Ruggieri, *Gazzetta*, 1925, **55**, 453; Werner, *Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1082.
2. *Gazzetta*, 1948, **78**, 536.
3. *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, **11B**, 268.
4. *Science & Culture*, 1952, **18**, 97; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, **154**, 103.
5. *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1392.
6. Dasgupta and Dhar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, **11B**, 520.

vanadium, and molybdenum⁷ have been made. Hydroxamic acids, in general, react with traces of vanadate in dilute solution producing in aqueous medium at pH 3 to 5 a brownish purple colour and in aqueous ethanol medium at the same pH range, a more intense golden yellow colour⁷.

Most of the workers in the field appeared to be interested in the utilisation of various hydroxamic acids as colorimetric reagents for vanadium and little attention was given to the co-ordination complexes that vanadium formed with these ligands.

Benzohydroxamic acid reacts in aqueous medium with ammonium vanadate in the pH range 3-4 to furnish a sparingly soluble and intensely coloured violet-black product. At pH 6-7, however, no precipitation occurs, instead a violet solution is formed. This, however, slowly decomposes on raising the pH to the alkaline side, due, no doubt, to the formation of alkali vanadates. The violet-black product corresponds to the analyses of a 1:2 compound and is diamagnetic. This is oxo-hydroxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V), $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$. The violet complex that exists in solution at pH 6-7 has been precipitated by Ba^{2+} and by stable bivalent complex cation, copper-bis-biguanidinium ion. These have the composition $\text{M}[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{R}_2]$ (where RH_2 = a molecule of benzohydroxamic acid, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CONHOH}$, and M = a bivalent cation). We have further observed that the recently synthesised copper-bis-guanylalkylureas⁸ can also be utilised for precipitating the complex ion $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})\text{R}_2]^{2-}$. The corresponding potassium salt was obtained as a gummy product which was difficult to purify. The barium-, copper-bis-biguanidinium-, and copper-bis-guanylethylurea salts were too insoluble to allow any conductance measurement. Since these salts are of the bi-bivalent type, one can appreciate that this cannot result through the ionisation of the hydroxyl group attached to vanadium, in which case the complex anion would have been univalent. The following reaction occurs at pH 6 to 7:

The hydroxamic acids therefore function as a dibasic acid at pH 6 or above. The complexes, thus isolated, are also diamagnetic.

The violet-black compound, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$, is insoluble in water, benzene, dichlorobenzene but is readily soluble in alcohols, giving an intense red colour. When the compound, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$, is refluxed with a small volume of methanol, ethanol, or isopropanol for an hour or so, the solution emits the characteristic smell of organic esters and on cooling in an ice bath deposits red to orange-red silky crystals. The analytical results for V, N, C, and H (Table I) provide evidence for presence of only one alkyl group per molecule of $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$. A compound of the type $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$ can be assumed to take up alkyl group, i.e., to undergo esterification at two possible points, either at the hydroxyl group or at the RH unit. During esterification of RH groups, both the RH groups may be expected to be esterified, thus taking two alkyl groups per $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$. It might be said that one of the two RH groups undergoes esterification first and the product, being less soluble (than the product where both the RH

7. Dutta, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 311; 1959, 36, 339; 1958, 35, 243.

8. Dutta and Ray, *ibid.*, 1959, 36, 587.

groups undergo esterification), crystallises readily on cooling. We have, however, repeatedly refluxed the compound, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$, with alcohols for longer periods and analysed the different fractions of the red crystals. In all cases, we have obtained analyses corresponding to one alkyl group. A further argument may be raised that one of the two RH groups in $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$ is probably strongly hydrogen-bonded to either 'O' or 'OH' in the complex zone, so that only one RH undergoes reaction with alcohols, whereas the other does not do so. We consider this rather unlikely. Instead, we find that the results could be explained more easily and with less ambiguity, if we consider that the vanadyl-OH group undergoes reaction with the alcohols. Since there is only one such point for reaction, we get mono-esters.

(where XOH stands for an aliphatic alcohol such as methanol, ethanol, or isopropanol).

TABLE I

Compound.	Calculated.				Found.
	% V.	% N.	% C.	% H.	
1. (a) $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{RH})_2]$	13.78	7.56	48.64	4.05	V : 13.68%
(b) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH}-\text{HO}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{RH})_2]$	13.14	7.21	46.39	4.38	N : 7.70
(c) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]$	13.28	7.29	50.00	4.42	C : 48.8
					H : 3.80
2. (a) $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{RH})_2]$	13.28	7.29	50.00	4.42	V : 13.05
(b) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH}\cdot\text{HOC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{RH})_2]$	12.88	6.96	47.76	4.72	N : 7.22
(c) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2]$	12.38	6.79	52.42	5.09	C : 49.80
					H : 4.60
3. (a) $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{RH})_2]$	12.81	7.03	51.25	4.77	V : 12.70
(b) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH}\cdot\text{HOC}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{RH})_2]$	12.26	6.72	49.03	5.05	N : 6.90
(c) $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{R}-\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_2]$	11.59	6.36	54.54	5.68	C : 50.80
					H : 4.00

Ebullioscopic determination of the molecular weight of the methyl ester in methanol gave a value of 362 (calc. for a monomer, 370), indicating its monomeric nature. The only other similar case is the reaction of recently investigated vanadium 8-hydroxyquinolate^{8a}. The black product, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(8\text{-hydroxyquinolate})_2]$, was found to react readily with alcohols to furnish red-coloured ester compounds of the type, $[\text{VO}(\text{OX})(8\text{-hydroxyquinolate})_2]$ ^{8a}. Incidentally, the compound $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(8\text{-hydroxyquinolate})_2]$ has practically no possibility of hydrogen bonding and further since after co-ordination, 8-hydroxyquinoline group has no site for taking up alkyl groups, the only site open to esterification is the 'OH' attached to vanadium. We have tried many alcohols and in all cases a red solution was obtained, but on concentration only a black compound was left behind. This probably suggests that the higher alcohols are merely hydrogen-bonded to $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$ and the reaction does not proceed further to furnish the red-coloured esters. Blair *et al.*^{8a} succeeded in obtaining even the amyl and the glycol esters with the vanadium 8-hydroxyquinolate.

Mention may be made here of the fact that so far no report has appeared in the literature describing such ester complexes of hydroxamic acids with other metals.

The compound $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$ is readily soluble in pyridine, developing a blue colour. It has not been possible, however, to isolate any blue compound from this medium.

Vanadyl sulphate reacts with benzohydroxamic acid at pH 3-4 to furnish a crystalline, rose-violet mass which has the composition $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2]$. The compound suffers no loss at 100° , but readily decomposes above 120° . This observation along with the analytical values {Found: N, 8.30; V, 14.80. Calc. for $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2]$: N, 8.25; V, 15.04%} is in accord with the 5-co-ordinated formula $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2]$. The compound is quite stable in air and shows no tendency towards oxidation. This is paramagnetic, giving a moment value of 1.72 B.M., indicative of quadrivalence of vanadium. The compound dissolves in ethanol giving first a pale red-violet solution, which on standing for about an hour produces a deep orange colour, indicating oxidation to vanadium (V) state. The spectrum in ethanol is quite comparable to those of vanadium (V) ester complexes in the same solvent. In fact, it has been possible to isolate silky red crystals of $[\text{VO}(\text{OX})(\text{RH})_2]$ by refluxing $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2]$ in alcohols. These crystals are indistinguishable from those obtained from the reaction of $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$ with alcohols.

Hydroxamic acid may be represented by two possible structures :

one hydroxamide and the other hydroxy-oxime structure. Tieman⁹ preferred the hydroxamide structure, whereas Lossen⁹ proposed the hydroxy-oxime structure. Plapinger¹⁰ from his ultraviolet absorption studies of a number of hydroxamic acids in acid and in alkaline media concluded that in the former medium the hydroxamide structure was the predominating species, whereas in the latter the hydroxy-oxime structure was more apparent. IR spectra of benzohydroxamic acid and some others were reported by Mathis¹¹. According to him, in solid state the spectra favour the hydroxamide structure, whereas in solution the hydroxy-oxime structure is indicated. Usova and Voroshin¹² also studied the IR spectra of benzohydroxamic acid and favoured the hydroxamide structure.

In order to elucidate further the structure of these reagents, we have also taken the IR spectra of potassium benzohydroxamate as also of its vanadium complexes, namely, $[\text{VO}(\text{RH})_2]$, $[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{RH})_2]$, and of $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{RH})_2]$. The absorption bands of the compounds are tabulated in Table II.

We consider the bands at 1307 cm^{-1} , 1611 cm^{-1} and 3175 cm^{-1} important from structural standpoint. It would be noted that during complex formation these bands are the ones most affected. The bands at 1307 cm^{-1} and at 1611 cm^{-1} are very much characteris-

9. *Chem. Rev.*, 1943, **33**, 209.

10. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1959, **24**, 803.

11. *Compt. rend.*, 1951, **232**, 505.

12. *Doklady Akad. Nauk, SSSR.*, 1957, **113**, 1306.

tic of mono-substituted amides. Usova and Voroshin¹² reported the C=O band at 1661 cm^{-1} in the free acid, whereas in our potassium salt it appears at 1611 cm^{-1} . This is quite expected. In fact, Mathis¹¹ reported this band at about 1620 cm^{-1} for the potassium salt. The characteristic IR absorption band for benzoyl¹³ group appears at 1600 cm^{-1} . In the event of a hydroxyoxime structure, the 'OH' would be expected to be strongly hydrogen-bonded which should appear as a broad band in the region 3200 cm^{-1} . We have, on the contrary, observed a very strong, narrow, and sharp absorption band at 3175 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of -NH-¹⁴. As such we have preferred the hydroxamide structure in the solid state.

TABLE II
Infrared spectra in KBr.
(Frequencies in cm^{-1} *)

KRH.	[VO(RH) ₂].	[VO(OH)(RH) ₂].	[VO(OCH)(RH) ₂].
696 b	699 b	690 b	685 b
792 s	790 s	784 b	785 b
896 s	916 s	920 s	920 s
	974 sh	968 s	966 s
	993 s		
1023 m	1023 m	1028 m	1043 s
1044 m			
1167 s	1150 s	1150 s	1152 s
1307 s, b	1346 s	1348 s	1348 s
1444 m	1444 s	1444 m	1444 m
1487 m	1479 s	1481 m	1483 m
1523 m	1513 m	1513 m	1513 m
1611 s	1595 s	1598 s	1595 s
3175 vs	3095 vs	3105 s, b	3100 s

* vs=very strong; s=strong; sh=shoulder; m=medium and b=broad.

On the basis of the above structure, the carbonyl oxygen will function as the donor atom in the metal complexes and the following resonating structures¹⁵ for the co-ordinating group are possible:

As a result, there will be electron withdrawal from the C=O group with a consequent increase in electron density in the 'CN' bond. Therefore, a lowering of the frequency of the carbonyl band and an increase of the C—N band (in the region 1300 cm^{-1}) are expected. The results confirm such expectations. In the reagent, the band at 3175 cm^{-1} might be considered to be due to N—H. During complex formation with vanadium, accumulation of a slight positive charge on the nitrogen atom occurs, which possibly lowers the N—H frequency. The band at 896 cm^{-1} in the ligand can also be related to C—N in addition to the one at 1307 cm^{-1} .

12. Gilman, "Organic Chemistry", Vol. III, John Wiley & Sons, N.Y., p. 144.

14. Meites and Thomas, "Advanced Analytical Chemistry", McGraw Hill Book Co., N.Y., 1958, p. 325.

15. Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", Cornell University Press, N.Y., 1938, p. 207.

It has been mentioned earlier that traces of ammonium vanadate produce with benzo hydroxamic acid in aqueous ethanol at pH 3 to 5 an intense orange-red colour, which was utilised by Das Gupta and Singh³ for the spectrophotometric estimation of vanadium. Since the ester compounds, isolated by us, also dissolved in alcohols producing an intense orange-red colour, we therefore proceeded to ascertain whether these same ester compounds were responsible for the colorimetric estimation of vanadium. Das Gupta and Singh³ determined the composition of the coloured complex by Job's method of continued variation and reported that V_2O_5 : benzo hydroxamic acid ratio in the coloured product was 1:2. This meant that the coloured entity was a 1:1 vanadium: benzo hydroxamic acid complex. This appeared to us to be highly improbable. We repeated the determination by Job's method several times at different dilutions and in all cases found that the maximum occurred when vanadium reacted with benzo hydroxamic acid in the ratio 1:3. The composition therefore indicated that the ester compound $[VO(OX)(RH)_2]$ was not involved in the colorimetry of vanadium in a dilute solution. We then compared the absorption spectra of the esters in ethanol with that of vanadate in presence of excess reagent in ethanol (aqueous). Whereas the coloured product involved in the colorimetry showed a sharp absorption maximum at 450 m μ with very high extinction coefficient, the ester complexes exhibited a flat absorption maximum at 430-440 m μ with lower extinction. We have further observed that when ethanol solution of the ester compound is treated with a further amount of benzo hydroxamic acid, an absorption spectrum is obtained which is almost superimposable on the spectra of the same amount of vanadate treated with a large excess of the reagent. The esters therefore react with still further amount of the reagent to produce the coloured complex involved in the colorimetry. We then ran some continued variation experiments between $[VO(OX)(RH)_2]$ and benzo hydroxamic acid and found that the peak occurred at 1:1. Undoubtedly, one can conclude that the coloured product, which Das Gupta and Singh³ worked on, is not a 1:1 complex, but a 1:3 complex.

TABLE III

Complex.	Medium.	λ_{max} .	Mol. extinc. coeff. (litre. mole ⁻¹ . cm ⁻¹).
1. $[VO(OH)(RH)_2]$	Ethanol	430 m μ	1652
2. $[VO(OCH_3)(RH)_2]$	"	430	1720
3. $[VO(OC_2H_5)(RH)_2]$	"	430	1710
4. $[VO(OC_3H_7)(RH)_2]$	"	430	1680
5. $[VO(OH)(RH)_2]$	Pyridine	480, 600	1324, 2736
6. Vanadium benzo hydroxamate	1:1 Aqueous ethanol	450	3760
7. $[VO(OC_2H_5)(RH)_2]$ and benzo hydroxamic-acid	"	450	3833

It now remains to see how the constitution of a 1:3 complex can be explained. The complex is found to be a non-electrolyte, retained neither by an anion exchanger (Amberlite IR 400) nor by a cation exchanger (Amberlite IR 120)*. Since three hydroxamic acid molecules are involved and further since the ligand behaves as bidentate in the solid complexes, one probable representation is $H(VR_3)$. Such a constitution, however,

*However, we consider that more exhaustive studies on the behaviour of this coloured species on different ion-exchange resins may be worthwhile.

cannot be readily accepted on the following grounds: (1) The complex will then be anionic and should be retained on an anion exchanger. (2) At pH 3, the ligands are not expected to exist in enol form. The formula, $[V(RH)_3]^{2+}$, too, cannot be accepted as it would be strongly retained on a cation-exchange resin bed.

In dilute solution, the ligands probably behave differently, functioning as unidentate monobasic ones instead of bidentate monobasic units. A structure of the type $[V(OH)_2(RH)_3]$ may therefore be suggested. In keeping with the observation made with the ester compounds, the hydroxyl groups of $[V(OH)_2(RH)_3]$ are supposed to be hydrogen-bonded to the alcohol molecules. The suggestion is, however, to be considered only tentative, as we are less certain of the actual structural disposition of the reacting groups in solution than when present in a solid complex.

At pH about 8 in aqueous medium or in aqueous ethanol medium, vanadate reacts with benzohydroxamic acid, forming a purple-coloured complex. This is less sensitive than the golden yellow one. Job's method indicates a 1:3 complex. This species can readily be given the anionic formula $H[VR_3]$. Since there is no hydroxyl group around vanadium, no formation of alcohol adducts is possible. This is in line with the observation that the species does not undergo any modification of colour on the addition of alcohol.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium benzohydroxamate was prepared by the interaction¹⁶ of methanolic hydroxylamine and ethyl benzoate.

Oxo-hydroxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V).—An aqueous solution of ammonium vanadate (0.1 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of potassium benzohydroxamate (0.4 g.); the pH of the violet solution was adjusted from nearly 7 to 3 by dilute H_2SO_4 (ca. 4*N*). The dark violet crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed well with water, and dried in vacuum over $CaCl_2$. {Found: N, 7.92; V, 14.25. $[VO(OH)(C_7H_6NO_2)_2]$ requires N, 7.86; V, 14.32%. $\chi_g = -0.463 \times 10^{-6}$ (35°). The compound is insoluble in water, benzene or dichlorobenzene, but dissolves in alcohols, forming a red solution. The compound gives a low molar conductance value ($1 \Lambda^{-1}$) in methanol.

Oxo-methoxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V).—The dark violet compound, prepared as described above, on refluxing with methanol (10 ml) for 1½ hrs. readily formed a red solution. The solution was filtered and the filtrate on cooling in ice-water yielded brick-red silky crystals. These were then filtered and dried over $CaCl_2$. {Found: C, 48.80; H, 3.80; N, 7.70; V, 13.68. $[VO(OCH_3)(C_7H_6NO_2)_2]$ requires C, 48.64; H, 4.05; N, 7.56; V, 13.87%. $\chi_g = -0.35 \times 10^{-6}$ (35°). This is insoluble in water, benzene or dichlorobenzene. The molecular weight of the compound was determined in methanol by the elevation of boiling point. (Found: 362; calc. for a monomer, 370).

Oxo-ethoxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V).—This brick-red compound was prepared by following the method adopted in the preceding compound using ethanol

16. Blatt, "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. II, p. 67.

(5-6 ml). {Found: C, 49.80; H, 4.60; N, 7.22; V, 13.05. $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires C, 50.00; H, 4.42; N, 7.29; V, 13.28%}.

Oxo-isopropoxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V) was prepared from the dark violet compound and isopropanol (4-5 ml), following methods described above. {Found: C, 50.80; H, 4.90; N, 6.90; V, 12.70. $[\text{VO}(\text{OC}_3\text{H}_7)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires C, 51.25; H, 4.77; N, 7.03; V, 12.81%}.

Barium [Oxo-hydroxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V)].—The clear violet solution developed at pH 7 by the action of aqueous ammonium vanadate (0.2 g) on potassium benzohydroxamate (0.7-0.8 g.) was treated with BaCl_2 solution. A crystalline dark violet precipitate deposited was filtered, washed well with water and alcohol, and dried (CaCl_2). {Found: N, 4.99; Ba, 23.97; V, 9.25; H_2O (by loss at 140°), 13.00. $\text{Ba}[\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_6\text{NO}_2)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 4.97; Ba, 24.30; V, 9.06; H_2O , 12.78%}. $\chi_g = -0.328 \times 10^{-6}$ (31°).

FIG. 1. Absorption spectra.

- (A) Complex, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell 2 cm.
 (B) Complex, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell 2 cm.
 (C) Complex, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell 2 cm.
 (D) Complex, 0.00025 *M*; solvent, ethanol; cell 2 cm.
 (E) Vanadium, 0.00025 *M*; benzohydroxamic acid, 150 times the metal; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.00; cell 1 cm.

Copper bis-biguanidinium(oxo-hydroxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium(V)) was prepared, following the earlier method using aqueous solution of copper bis-biguanide chloride in place of BaCl_2 solution. {Found: N, 24.30; Cu, 9.08; V, 7.58; H_2O (by loss at 130°), 10.00. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}_3)_2][\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 24.28; Cu, 9.18; V, 7.37; H_2O , 10.41%}.

FIG. 2. Absorption spectra.

A. $\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{PhCONHO})_2$ in pyridine.
B to E. $\text{VO}(\text{PhCONHO})_2$ in EtOH.

- (A) Complex, 0.00025M; solvent, pyridine; cell 1 cm.
(B) Complex, 0.00025M; solvent, ethanol; cell 1 cm; after 45 minutes of dissolving.
(C) Complex, 0.00025M; solvent, ethanol; cell 1 cm after 75 minutes of dissolving.
(D) Complex, 0.00025M; solvent, ethanol; cell 1 cm; after 120 minutes of dissolving.
(E) Complex, 0.00025M; ethanol; cell 1 cm; after 300 minutes of dissolving.

Copper bis-guanylethylurea[oxo-hydroxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium(V)] was obtained as above, using aqueous solution of copper bis-guanylethylurea chloride in place of BaCl_2 solution. {Found: N, 18.60; Cu, 8.68; V, 6.7; H_2O (by loss at 120°), 9.25. $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_4\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O})_2][\text{VO}(\text{OH})(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2] \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 18.67; Cu, 8.47; V, 6.80; H_2O , 9.60%}.

Oxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (IV).—An aqueous solution of vanadyl sulphate (0.25 g.) was added to an aqueous solution of potassium benzohydroxamate (0.45 g.) when the rose-violet crystalline precipitate separated at pH (*ca.*) 3-4. This was then digested on a water bath for few minutes, washed repeatedly with water, filtered, and dried in vacuum (CaCl_2). {Found: N, 8.30; V, 14.80. $[\text{VO}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires N, 8.25; V, 15.04%}. The product gave a paramagnetic susceptibility. $\chi_M(\text{corr}) \times 10^6 = 1189$; diamagnetic correction $\times 10^6 = 158.5$; $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.72$ B.M. (35°).

The substance dissolves in alcohol, giving initially a pale red-violet colour which gradually deepened to red. On refluxing these crystals in methanol on a water bath for an hour or so and on cooling in an ice bath, a crop of brick-red crystals was obtained. These were diamagnetic and on analysis were found to be oxo-methoxo-bis-benzohydroxamato-vanadium (V). {Found: N, 7.49; V, 13.80. $[\text{VO}(\text{OCH}_3)(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2)_2]$ requires N, 7.56; V, 13.87%}. $\chi_g = -0.4 \times 10^{-5}$ (35°).

VANADIUM: BENZOHYDROXAMIC ACID COMPLEXES

*Job's Method*¹⁷ of *Continued Variation*.—Equimolar 1:1 aqueous ethanolic ammonium vanadate and benzohydroxamic acid solutions were mixed, pH adjusted around 3.0, and the volume made to 50 ml. The optical density of these solutions was measured in 2 cm cells with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer or a UVISpek Hilger spectrophotometer at different wave lengths. Optical densities of the metal ion under identical condition was recorded. The difference in optical density was then plotted against mole fraction of the reagent.

Similar continued variation studies were also carried out between oxo-methoxy-bis-benzohydroxamate-vanadium(V) and benzohydroxamic acid. Corrections for the ester complex were done under comparable conditions (Figs. 3 and 4).

Fig. 3. Job's curves of vanadium benzohydroxamate.

- (A) Vanadium, 0.001 *M*; benzohydroxamic acid, 0.001 *M*; metal + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.00; cell 2 cm.
- (B) Same as in A.
- (C) Vanadium, 0.002 *M*; benzohydroxamic acid 0.0002 *M*; metal + reagent = 15 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH, 3.05; cell 2 cm.
- (D) Same as in C.
- (E) Vanadium, 0.005 *M*; benzohydroxamic acid, 0.005 *M*; metal + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.60; cell 2 cm.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectra of the different vanadium complexes were taken in ethanol. The concentrations in all cases were maintained at 0.00025 *M*. The spectrum of the coloured species involved in colorimetry was recorded in presence of a large excess of the reagent (V: reagent about 1:150) (Figs. 1 and 2).

Fig. 4. Job's curves.

- (A) Complex, 0.0006 M ; benzohydroxamic acid, 0.0006 M ; complex + reagent = 40 ml; total volume = 50 ml; solvent, 1:1 aqueous ethanol; pH 3.02; cell 2cm.
(B) Same as in A.

Magnetic Measurements.—These were carried out as in the previous communication¹⁶.

Thanks are due to Prof. K. Banerjee, Director of this Institution for providing laboratory facilities. Thanks are also due to Prof. J. N. Chatterjea of Science College, Patna and to Mrs. C. Dutta of this institute for carbon and hydrogen determinations.